

COMPARING MATERIALS USED TO REPAIR DENTAL DECAY: IMPACT ON PATIENT HEALTH

USE OF AMALGAM IN DENTAL RESTORATIONS

From 2034, the UK and Europe will stop using dental amalgam (a metal filling material) to repair cavities (tooth decay). Dentists may still use amalgam in special cases if it is best for the patient. However, other filling materials, such as glass ionomer and resin composites, may be used more often.

This change follows a gradual move away from using amalgam in the UK and other countries. Some people have concerns about how amalgam affects human health, especially because it contains mercury. We know less about how other materials affect human health

SUPPORTING RESEARCH

Prior to the decision to stop using dental amalgam in the UK, the Exeter Policy Research Programme (PRP) Evidence Review Facility were asked to independently complete a systematic review for the Department of Health and Social Care to find out more about the health impact of amalgam compared to other materials used to repair tooth decay.*

KEY FINDINGS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

- **Current research does not clearly show how different dental filling materials affect health. At the moment, we cannot say that one material is safer than another.**
- **Fewer studies look at the health affects of composite resin and glass ionomer fillings. This is something that needs more research. Groups to focus on include dentists and pregnant women.**
- **Patients should be told about possible health effects of different fillings and involved in deciding which material to use.**
- **Please speak to your dentist if you have any concerns about issues relating to this research.**

Properties of different materials used to repair dental decay

Key definitions

DENTAL AMALGAM: Made from mercury mixed with metals such as silver, tin, and copper.

RESIN BASED COMPOSITE: Tooth-coloured and made from plastic resin and tiny glass or ceramic particles.

GLASS IONOMER: Tooth-coloured and made from glass powder. It bonds to the tooth and releases fluoride to help stop decay.

WHAT IS A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW?

A systematic review brings together studies on the same topic to answer a question. It checks whether the studies show similar results. It also looks at how well the studies were carried out to see how much we can trust the findings

*This review also looked at how different filling materials may affect the environment. Please see the separate patient information leaflet for more details.

SYSTEMATIC REVIEW FINDINGS: FURTHER DETAIL

61 studies looked at how different types of dental materials affected human health. The most common health areas were: **Allergy, General health, Musculoskeletal (muscles and bones), Neurological (nerves and brain), Neuropsychological (thinking and memory), Oral health (mouth and teeth), and Psychosocial (emotions and wellbeing)** symptoms.

Amalgam vs Composite Resin	Amalgam only	Composite resin
<p>Only 6 studies compared the health impacts of these two filling materials.</p> <p>We found some differences for neuropsychological and psychosocial symptoms, but one type of material was not always better than the other.</p>	<p>10 studies looked how exposure to amalgam during pregnancy might affect infant health. The health areas supported by the most evidence were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pregnancy outcomes: More research is needed to understand whether having more amalgam fillings could affect risk of miscarriage. <p>Weak evidence suggests that exposure to amalgam during pregnancy is not linked to birth defects.</p>	<p>15 studies looked at how composite resin fillings affect health.</p> <p>Greater exposure to resin-based composite was linked to poorer psychosocial health</p> <p>BUT</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• the small number of studies,• different people they included,• and different outcome measured, <p>mean we cannot trust these findings.</p>
<p>Because there is very little research, we cannot be sure whether amalgam and composite resin affect health differently.</p>	<p>36 studies looked at amalgam and patient health.</p> <p>The studies were very different, so firm conclusions are difficult.</p> <p>A very small amount of research suggests amalgam may affect:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Immune system• Muscles and bones• Some mouth problems <p>No link was found between amalgam and thinking or memory tests.</p> <p>We need more high quality research to increase trust in these findings.</p>	<p>We need more high quality research to look at the effect of composite resin across all health areas.</p>
<p>Glass ionomer vs Composite resin:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Only 3 studies compared how glass ionomer and composite resin affect health.• The studies looked at different outcomes and had very different results, so we cannot say which material is safer		

Exeter PRP Evidence Review Facility

We are one of two research groups in the UK commissioned by the National Institute of Health and Care Research Policy Research Programme to conduct syntheses of evidence to inform policy development and evaluation across the full policy remit of the DHSC. The views expressed are those of the authors and not necessarily those of the DHSC.